

CAPABLE

Cancer Patients Better Life Experience

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R	Document, report	
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DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos etc.	
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PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential (Consortium members including the Commission Services)	
CI	Classified Information (Commission Decision 2015/444/EC)	

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1. Version history

Version	Date	Author	Comments
1.0	10/6/2022	Matteo Gabetta (BIOM)	

2. Executive summary

The aim of this deliverable is to support and provide context to the CAPABLE system demonstration video which is available at [this link](#). A brief description about the scope of the demonstration is followed by a detailed description of the scenario that will be managed during the demo.

The demonstration video was recorded in the second half of June 2022; the demo will also be shown during the consortium meeting that will happen next July 12th and 13th, 2022.

Given the decoupled nature of the CAPABLE architecture, the efforts that led to the completion of this demo were twofold: on the one hand, each involved partner carried out the development of the component under their own responsibility, on the other hand there was a global effort to make the different components communicate with each other. All these efforts have been coordinated by Task Force 1, focused on the development of the final CAPABLE architecture.

A new time-simulation method has been devised to make sure that all the components were reasoning at the current time. Moreover, a dedicated simulator has been implemented automatically loading and adjusting the time stamps of the Resource to comply with the method. For this demonstration, in addition, the scenario was created based on real patient data.

3. Scope of the demo

The demonstration involves most of the components of the CAPABLE architecture described in Figure 1 and covers many interactions between them; in particular, the included components are:

- Data Platform (DP), storing and providing patient-level data,
- Case Manager (CM), managing events related to Data Platform and providing notifications to other components,
- Knowledge-Data Ontology Mapper (KDOM), computing abstractions from data stored in the DP,
- Deontics Engine, executing computer-interpretable clinical practice guidelines (CIGs) defined using the PROforma language,
- GoCom Multimorbidity controller, checking for possible adverse interactions between clinical tasks for multimorbid patients and resolving them. Currently, it focuses on drug-drug interactions, but it can be extended to other types of interactions involving non-clinical tasks (e.g., physical exercises).
- Physician DSS, providing guideline-based decision support for clinicians when managing cancer patients.
- Virtual Coach (VC), providing coaching support combining clinical (guideline-based) and non-clinical recommendations to cancer patients staying at home.

The Deontics Engine is used by both Physician DSS and Virtual Coach (more precisely, they use different instances of the Engine). Moreover, GoCom queries the Deontics Engine when checking for possible adverse interactions between tasks to get detailed characteristics of CIG tasks. Interactions between Deontics Engine and other components are handled by a web-based (REST) API. GoCom is invoked by Physician DSS and Virtual Coach -- in such case communication employs Data Platform and Case Manager.

All components have been effectively deployed in the premises made available by the partners responsible for their development; thus, all the interactions between these components that are shown in the demo are happening live.

The demonstration leverages the CAPABLE simulator [1], a software component designed and developed specifically to support the test phase of the system that precedes production. The simulator allows to divide the simulated scenario into several successive segments and to independently test their correct execution; in fact, by passing from one segment to another, the component recreates the situation (i.e., the FHIR resources) present at the end of the segment that precedes it within the Data Platform. In this way, during the test phase, on the one hand any error or missing data are promptly detected (through the ability of the simulator to verify the correctness of the scene at the end of each segment) but, on the other hand, they do not block the execution of future segments, thus allowing testing of entire scenarios.

In this deliverable, all aspects related to the two graphical user interfaces (GUIs) of the system have been deliberately left out, to avoid overlapping with the deliverable D6.3 dedicated to them. All resources created by the GUIs are managed by the CAPABLE simulator.

Figure 1. The CAPABLE overall architecture.

4.Scenario

The demo, designed together with clinicians and patients involved in the project, focuses on a single clinical guideline: the “Diarrhea in adult cancer patients: ESMO Clinical Practice Guidelines” [2]; and it revolves around a patient fictionally named Maria Rossi. Maria is 67 years old, and she’s affected by renal cancer; apart from her main diagnosis, Maria has no significant clinical history. The demo follows Maria during the period spanning from January 7th to January 24th, 2022, starting from the enrollment visit (day 0) where the clinician inserts relevant clinical data and oncological therapies (one immunotherapy and one targeted therapy) associated to the patient.

After seven days (day 0) Maria begins to experience the side effects of cancer therapy and reports the symptom of diarrhea. Thanks to the ESMO guideline dedicated to diarrhea implemented in CAPABLE, the system supports (from day 0 to day 10) the management of the adverse effect both by sending pharmacological suggestions to the clinician and by sending tips to the patient until the symptom ends.

The scenario is divided in 13 segments, executed in sequence, and verified by the CAPABLE simulator. In the following paragraphs each segment will be briefly introduced.

4.1. Segment 1 - Enrollment

- Physician, through Physician App, enrolls Maria Rossi.
- Relevant values provided at enrollment:
 - Date of birth: 11/11/1954
 - Gender: Female
 - Weight: 62 kg
 - Height: 160 cm
 - Ongoing immunotherapy: Nivolumab
 - Ongoing targeted therapy: Sunitinib
 - Ongoing cancer medication list: Nivolumab, Sunitinib
 - Ongoing use of immunotherapy that may cause diarrhea : Present
 - Ongoing use of targeted therapy that may cause diarrhea : Present
- Since the patient is under Sunitinib treatment (showing 44% incidence of diarrhea), the CIG recommends the oncologist to prescribe "Loperamide as needed", providing the motivation “The incidence of therapy-induced diarrhea for the patient's cancer treatment is higher than the threshold”. As a matter of fact, the oncologists suggested 40% as the diarrhea incidence threshold for prescribing Loperamide as-needed.

4.2. Segment 2 - Loperamide prescription

- The clinician accepts the recommendation and prescribes Loperamide
- On the patient app, VC provides to the patient the new prescription to take Loperamide if needed

4.3. Segment 3 - Day 0

4.3.1. Patient Guideline Execution

- The CIG checks if “Loperamide as needed” is a prescribed treatment. (YES, Loperamide as needed is prescribed)
- VC provides to the patient a random AIMAC tip from the ones eligible for the patient
- Patient Maria Rossi, through the Patient app, inserts the symptom diarrhea grade 1.
- The GUIs asks her if she also has additional symptoms such as vomiting, nausea, fever, dizziness, cramps, bloody stools and abdominal pain (this is because if one or more of those additional symptoms are present, the diarrhea is defined as “complicated” and needs a different management).

- Maria doesn't report any other symptom
- VC sends self-care instructions to the patient
- The patient receives the self-care instructions
- VC checks if the Loperamide has been prescribed as needed and requests KDOM to compute Complicated Diarrhea abstraction
- KDOM computes the abstraction (FALSE, no complicated Diarrhea)
- Since there is no complicated diarrhea and Loperamide was prescribed "as needed", VC sends the recommendation "Take Loperamide" to Maria

4.3.2. Physician Guideline Execution

- Patient Maria Rossi, through Patient app, inserted the symptom diarrhea grade 1.
- The CIG checks the abstraction "Complicated Diarrhea" (FALSE, no complicated Diarrhea)
- The CIG checks the abstraction "Diarrhea Persistent" and the result is (FALSE, no persistent Diarrhea)
- The Physician receives recommendations regarding also:
 - Uncomplicated diarrhea initial management
 - Loperamide

4.4. Segment 4 – Day 2 start

- VC after 48 hour asks for symptom update

4.5. Segment 5 – Day 2

4.5.1. Patient Guideline Execution

- Patient Maria Rossi, through Patient app, inserts the symptom diarrhea grade 2
- The GUIs asks her if she also has the related symptoms vomiting, nausea, fever, dizziness, cramps, bloody stools and abdominal pain.
- She doesn't report any other symptom
- VC sends the contact level for symptom diarrhea, grade 2: "Please, contact the oncological team" ("Contact levels" are immediate feedback sent to the patient every time she enters or updates a symptom. They are meant to reassure the patient that CAPABLE, and if necessary the doctors, are taking care for the situation)
- VC checks if the Loperamide has been prescribed as needed and requests KDOM to compute Complicated Diarrhea abstraction
- KDOM computes the abstraction (True, Complicated Diarrhea- As a matter of fact, even if there are no other symptoms, a grade 2 diarrhea under immunotherapy is defined as complicated)
- VC sends recommendation "Take Loperamide"

4.5.2. Physician Guideline Execution

- Patient Maria Rossi, through Patient app, inserted the symptom diarrhea grade 2.
- The CIG checks the abstraction "Complicated Diarrhea" (TRUE, complicated Diarrhea)
- The CIG checks the abstraction "Diarrhea Persistent" and the result is (FALSE, no persistent Diarrhea)
- Physician receives recommendations regarding also (all the following drugs could be used for diarrhea):
 - Codeine
 - Morphine
 - Opium Tincture
 - Loperamide
 - Hospital admission
 - Oral rehydration

and

- Suspend immunotherapy
- The clinician selects oral rehydration and accepts to suspend the immunotherapy
- The patient receives prescriptions through the Patient App

4.6. Segment 6 – Day 4 start

- VC after 48 hour asks for symptom update

4.7. Segment 7 – Day 4

4.7.1. Patient Guideline Execution

- Patient Maria Rossi, through Patient app, inserts the symptom diarrhea grade 3
- The GUIs asks her if she also has the related symptoms vomiting, nausea, fever, dizziness, cramps, bloody stools and abdominal pain.
- She doesn't report any other symptom
- VC sends the contact level for symptom diarrhea, grade 3: "Please, contact the oncological team"
- Maria Rossi, through the Patient App, receives the recommendation "In the meanwhile, please follow the treatment that the physician prescribed for your symptom"
- Maria contacts the clinician and the clinician sets up a visit on 20/01/2022

4.8. Segment 8 – Day 5 reminder

- Patient Maria Rossi receives the reminder of the appointment

4.9. Segment 9 – Day 6

4.9.1. Physician Guideline Execution

- Physician visits the patient and confirms in the physician dashboard a diarrhea grade 3 (caused by the cancer treatment)
- The CIG checks the abstraction "Diarrhea Persistent" and the result is (TRUE, persistent Diarrhea)
- Physician receives recommendations regarding:
 - Hospital admission
 - Octreotide
 - Intravenous rehydration
- The clinician selects intravenous rehydration to be performed at the hospital

4.10. Segment 10 – Day 8 start

- VC after 48 hours asks for symptom update

4.11. Segment 11 – Day 8

4.11.1. Patient Guideline Execution

- Patient Maria Rossi, through Patient app, inserts the symptom diarrhea grade 1
- The GUIs asks her if she also has the related symptoms vomiting, nausea, fever, dizziness, cramps, bloody stools and abdominal pain.
- She doesn't report any other symptom
- VC sends self-care instructions to the patient
- The patient receives the self-care instructions
- VC checks if the Loperamide has been prescribed as needed and requests KDOM to compute Complicated Diarrhea abstraction
- KDOM computes the abstraction (FALSE, no complicated Diarrhea)
- Since there is no complicated diarrhea and Loperamide was prescribed "as needed", VC sends recommendation "Take Loperamide"

4.11.2. Physician Guideline Execution

- Patient Maria Rossi, through Patient app, inserted the symptom diarrhea grade 1.
- The CIG checks the abstraction "Complicated Diarrhea" (FALSE, no complicated Diarrhea)
- The CIG checks the abstraction "Diarrhea Persistent" and the result is (FALSE, no persistent Diarrhea)
- Physician receives recommendations regarding also:
 - Uncomplicated diarrhea management
- The clinician doesn't select anything

4.12. Segment 12 – Day 10 start

- VC provides to the patient a random AIMAC tip from the ones eligible for the patient
- VC after 48 hour asks for symptom update

4.13. Segment 13 – Day 10

4.13.1. Patient Guideline Execution

- Patient Maria Rossi, through Patient app, answers NO, no symptoms present
- VC sends the recommendation "Share your experience" (if she wants, Maria can access the AIMAC forum and explain to other patients how she effectively managed her symptom)
- The patient guideline stops because diarrhea is solved

4.13.2. Physician Guideline Execution

- Patient Maria Rossi, through Patient app, inserted the symptom diarrhea was gone
- The physician resumes the anticancer therapy Nivolumab
- The CIG stops because diarrhea is solved

5. Summary

This document describes CAPABLE Platform 3rd Iteration demonstration (M30). Since the 2nd iteration [3], the platform has undergone several major upgrades:

- All components are now actually deployed at the premises provided by each responsible partner
- Each component is now in a “candidate release” stage, next 6 months will be dedicated to test the system in the hospital premises and, in case, fix/improve components’ features
- Simulation of time has undergone a new major redesign and is now able to effectively provide support for a complete internal testing

Furthermore, the CAPABLE deployment strategy is now fully operational: two environments, each one holding all the CAPABLE components interacting with each other, are maintained by the consortium: “Integration Test Platform”, a stable environment for integration testing and demos, and “Component Development Platform”, an unstable environment for continuous integration.

6. References

- [1] LANZOLA G., POLCE F. et al. Designing a Testing Environment for the CAPABLE Telemonitoring and Coaching Platform. Proceedings of the IEEE MELECON Conference 2022 (to appear).
- [2] HAANEN, J. B. A. G., et al. Management of toxicities from immunotherapy: ESMO Clinical Practice Guidelines for diagnosis, treatment and follow-up. *Annals of Oncology*, 2017, 28: iv119-iv142.
- [3] CAPABLE D4.2: 2nd Iteration of the Platform Proof Of Concept - <https://zenodo.org/record/5159100#.Yrwp4uxBxaQ>